

KOMPLEKS O'ZGARUVCHILI FUNKSIYANING DIFFERENTIALLANUVCHANLIGI. KOSHI- RIMAN SHARTLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Mening ilmiy tadqiqot ishimda kompleks o'zgaruvchili funksiya orttirmasi, kompleks o'zgaruvchili funksiya hosilasi va funksiya differensiallanuvchanligi, haqiqiy o'zgaruvchili funksiyalar hosilasi bilan o'xshash xossalari va farqlari hamda Koshi-Riman shartlari, kompleks argumentli golomorf funksiyalar, antigolomorf funksiyalar, garmonik funksiyalar bilan bog'liqlik formulalarini nostandart usullarini o'rganish va tahlil qilib, mavjud muammolarini matematik yechimini topish bo'yicha tadqiqotlar amalga oshirilgan va nazriy asoslangan.

Tayanch iboralar: Funksiya orttirmasi, funksiya hosilasi, funksiya differensiallanuvchanligi, Koshi-Riman shartlari, C-differensiallanuvchi funksiyalar, golomorf funksiyalar, antigolomorf funksiyalar, garmonik funksiyalar.

$W = f(z)$ funksiya $E \subset C$ to'plamda berilgan bo'lsin. Bu E to'plamda z_0 nuqtani olib unga shunday orttirma beraylikki, $z_0 + \Delta z \in E$ bo'lsin. Natijada $f(z)$ funksiya ham z_0 nuqtada

$$\Delta W = \Delta f(z_0) = f(z_0 + \Delta z) - f(z_0)$$

orttirmaga ega bo'ladi.

1-ta'rif. Aagar $\Delta z \rightarrow 0$ da $\frac{\Delta W}{\Delta z}$ nisbatning limiti

$$\lim_{\Delta z \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta W}{\Delta z} = \lim_{\Delta z \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(z_0 + \Delta z) - f(z_0)}{\Delta z}$$

mavjud va chekli bo'lsa, bu limit kompleks o'zgaruvchili $f(z)$ funksiyaning z_0 nuqtadagi hosilasi deb aytiladi va $f'(z_0)$ kabi belgilanadi:

$$f'(z_0) = \lim_{\Delta z \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(z_0 + \Delta z) - f(z_0)}{\Delta z}$$

2-ta'rif: Agar $f(z)$ funksiya $z_0 \in E$ nuqta $f'(z_0)$ hosilaga ega bo'lsa, funksiya z_0 nuqtada differensiallanuvchi deyiladi.

Agar $f(z)$ funksiya E to'plamning har bir nuqtasida differensiallanuvchi bo'lsa, funksiya E to'plamda differensiallanuvchi deyiladi.

Aytaylik, $f(z)$ funksiya z_0 nuqtada $f'(z_0)$ hosilaga ega bo'lsin. Unda

$$\lim_{\Delta z \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta f(z_0)}{\Delta z} = f'(z_0)$$

bo'lib,

$$\Delta f(z_0) = f'(z_0)\Delta z + \alpha(z_0, \Delta z) \cdot \Delta z$$

bo'ladi. Bu yerda $\Delta z \rightarrow 0$ da $\alpha(z_0, \Delta z)$ ham nolga intiladi: $\alpha(z_0, \Delta z) \rightarrow 0$

1-teorema. $f(z)$ funksiyaning $z_0 \in E$ nuqtada differensiallanuvchi bo'lishi uchun uning orttirmasi $\Delta f(z_0)$ ni ushbu

$$\Delta f(z_0) = A\Delta z + \alpha(z_0, \Delta z) \cdot \Delta z$$

Ko'rinishda ifodalanishi zarur va etarli.

Bunda A miqdor Δz hamda $\alpha(z_0, \Delta z)$ larga bog'liq bo'lmagan miqdordir.

Misol. 1) $f(z) = x - iy = \bar{z}$

$$\lim_{z \rightarrow z_0} \frac{x - iy}{x + iy} - \text{mavjud emas}$$

$$z = x + iy. \quad f(z) = z = x + iy$$

$$\lim_{z \rightarrow z_0} \frac{f(z) - f(z_0)}{z - z_0} = \frac{z - z_0}{z - z_0} = 1$$

2-teorema. Agar $f(z)$ va $g(z)$ funksiya nuqtada hosilaga ega bo'lsalar, u holda

$$f(z) \pm g(z), \quad f(z) \cdot g(z), \quad \frac{f(z)}{g(z)} \quad (g(z_0) \neq 0)$$

funksiyalar ham hosilaga ega bo'ladi. Bu hosilalar analizda o'tilgan formula orqali topiladi. Isboti ham xuddi shunday bo'ladi

Natija. 1) Ixtiyoriy $P(z) = a_0 z^n + \dots + a_n z$ ko'pxad kompleks tekislikni ixtiyoriy nuqtasida hosilaga egadir.

2) Ixtiyoriy $R(z) = \frac{P(z)}{Q(z)}$ ratsional funksiya $Q(z) \neq 0$ nuqtadan tashqarida hosilaga egadir.

Faraz qilaylik,

$$f(z) = u(x, y) + iv(x, y)$$

funksiya biror D sohada ($D(S)$ berilgan bo'lib, $z_0 = x_0 + iy_0 \in D$ bo'lsin.

3- ta'rif: Agar haqiqiy o'zgaruvchili $u(x, y)$ va $v(x, y)$ funksiyalar (x_0, y_0) nuqta da $((x_0, y_0) \in R^2)$ diferensiallanuvchi bo'lsa, $f(z)$ funksiya z_0 nuqta da haqiqiy analiz ma'nosida (kiskacha R^2 ma'noda) diferensiallanuvchi deyiladi.

3-teorema. $f(z)$ funksiyaning z_0 nuqta da $f'(z_0)$ hosilaga ega bo'lishi uchun

1. $f(z)$ ning nuqta da haqiqiy analiz ma'nosida diferensiallanuvchi bo'lishi va
2. ushbu

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}, \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial v}{\partial x}$$

(1)

Koshi-Riman shartlarining bajarilishi zarur va etarli.

Misol.

$$f(z) = x - iy$$

$$u = x, \quad v = -y \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = 1, \quad \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = -1 \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \neq \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}$$

Teorema isboti. Zarurligi.

$f(z)$ funksiya $z_0 \in (D)$ nuqtada $f'(z_0)$ hosilaga ega bo'lsin. Hosila ta'rifiga ko'ra

$$\lim_{\Delta z \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta f(z_0)}{\Delta z} = f'(z_0),$$

ya'ni

$$\Delta f(z_0) = f'(z_0) \cdot \Delta z + \alpha \Delta z$$

bo'ladi. Bu erda

$$\Delta z = z - z_0 = (x + iy) - (x_0 + iy_0) = (x - x_0) + i(y - y_0) = \Delta x + i\Delta y.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta f(z_0) &= f(z) - f(z_0) = [u(x, y) + iv(x, y)] - [u(x_0, y_0) + iv(x_0, y_0)] = \\ &= [u(x, y) - u(x_0, y_0)] + i[v(x, y) - v(x_0, y_0)] = \Delta u + i\Delta v \end{aligned}$$

bo'lib, α esa Δx va Δy larga bog'liq va ular nolga intilganda nolga intiladi

.

$$\lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0, \Delta y \rightarrow 0} \alpha = 0$$

Endi $f'(z_0)$ hamda α larni

$$f'(z_0) = a + ib, \quad \alpha = \alpha_1 + i\alpha_2 \quad \left(\lim_{\substack{\Delta x \rightarrow 0 \\ \Delta y \rightarrow 0}} \alpha_1 = \lim_{\substack{\Delta x \rightarrow 0 \\ \Delta y \rightarrow 0}} \alpha_2 = 0 \right)$$

deb, (2) tenglikni quyidagiga yozamiz:

$$\Delta u + i\Delta v = (a + ib)(\Delta x + i\Delta y) + (\alpha_1 + i\alpha_2)(\Delta x + i\Delta y)$$

Bu tenglikdan, haqiqiy hamda mavhum qismlarini tenglab topamiz:

$$\Delta u = a\Delta x - b\Delta y + \alpha_1\Delta x - \alpha_2\Delta y$$

$$\Delta v = b\Delta x - a\Delta y + \alpha_2\Delta x - \alpha_1\Delta y$$

Demak, $u(x, y)$ va $v(x, y)$ funksiyalar (x_0, y_0) nuqtada differensiallanuvchi. Ayni paytda $f(z)$ funksiya nuqta da R^2 ma'noda differensiallanuvchi bo'ladi.

Modomiki, $f(z)$ funksiya nuqta da $f'(z_0)$ hosilaga ega ekan, unda, $\Delta z \rightarrow 0$

jumladan $\Delta z = \Delta x \rightarrow 0$ ($\Delta y = 0$), $\Delta z = \Delta y \rightarrow 0$ ($\Delta x = 0$),

bo'lganda ham

$$\frac{\Delta f(z_0)}{\Delta z}$$

nisbatning limiti har doim $f'(z_0)$ ga teng bo'laveradi.

(3) tengliklar $\Delta z = \Delta x$ ($\Delta y = 0$), bo'lganda $\Delta u = a\Delta x + \alpha_1\Delta x$
 $\Delta v = b\Delta x + \alpha_2\Delta x$

(4) $\Delta z = \Delta y$ ($\Delta x = 0$), bo'lganda esa $\Delta u = -\epsilon\Delta y - \alpha_2\Delta y$
 $\Delta v = a\Delta y + \alpha_1\Delta y$

(5) tengliklarga keladi. (4) munosabatdan

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = a, \quad \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = \epsilon$$

(5) munosabatdan esa

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -\epsilon, \quad \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = a$$

bo'lishini topamiz. Bu tengliklardan

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}, \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial v}{\partial x},$$

bo'lishi kelib chiqadi.

Etarlilik. Aytaylik $f(z)$ funksiya z_0 nuqtada R^2 ma'noda differentsiallanuvchi bo'lib, teoremda keltirilgan ikkinchi shart bajarilsin. $u(x, y)$ va $v(x, y)$ funksiyalar (x_0, y_0) nuqtada differentsiallanuvchi bo'lgani uchun

$$\Delta u = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \Delta x - \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \Delta y + \alpha_1 \Delta x - \alpha_2 \Delta y$$

$$\Delta v = \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \Delta x - \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \Delta y + \beta_1 \Delta x - \beta_2 \Delta y$$

bo'ladi. Bu erda $\Delta x \rightarrow 0$, $\Delta y \rightarrow 0$ da α_1, α_2 , β_1, β_2 larning har biri nolga intiladi. U holda

$$\Delta f(z_0) = \Delta u + i\Delta v = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \Delta x - \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \Delta y + \alpha_1 \Delta x - \alpha_2 \Delta y + i \left[\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \Delta x - \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \Delta y + \beta_1 \Delta x - \beta_2 \Delta y \right]$$

bo'ladi. Teoremani ikkinchi sharti

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}, \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial v}{\partial x},$$

dan foydalanib topamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta f(z_0) &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} (\Delta x + i\Delta y) - i \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} (\Delta x + i\Delta y) + (\alpha_1 + i\beta_1) \Delta x + (\alpha_2 + i\beta_2) \Delta y = \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - i \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) \Delta z + \left[(\alpha_1 + i\beta_1) \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta z} + (\alpha_2 + i\beta_2) \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta z} \right] \Delta z \end{aligned}$$

Bu tenglikdan esa

$$\frac{\Delta f(z_0)}{\Delta z} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - i \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + (\alpha_1 + i\beta_1) \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta z} + (\alpha_2 + i\beta_2) \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta z}$$

bo'lishi kelib chiqadi.

Keyingi tenglikdagi

$$(\alpha_1 + i\beta_1) \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta z} + (\alpha_2 + i\beta_2) \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta z}$$

ifoda uchun

$$\begin{aligned} \left| (\alpha_1 + i\beta_1) \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta z} + (\alpha_2 + i\beta_2) \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta z} \right| &\leq |(\alpha_1 + i\beta_1)| \left| \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta z} \right| + |(\alpha_2 + i\beta_2)| \left| \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta z} \right| \leq \\ &\leq |\alpha_1 + i\beta_1| + |\alpha_2 + i\beta_2| \leq |\alpha_1| + |\beta_1| + |\alpha_2| + |\beta_2| < \varepsilon \end{aligned}$$

bo'ladi, chunki $\Delta z \rightarrow 0$ da ya'ni $\Delta x \rightarrow 0$, $\Delta y \rightarrow 0$ da

Shuni e'tiborga olib (6) tenglikda $\Delta z \rightarrow 0$ da limitga utib

$$\lim_{\Delta z \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta f(z_0)}{\Delta z} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - i \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}$$

bo'lishini topamiz. Demak., $f(z)$ funksiya nuqta da $f'(z_0)$ hosilaga ega va

$$f'(z_0) = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - i \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}$$

bo'ladi. Teorema isbot bo'ldi.

Eslatma. Yuqorida keltirilgan teorema $f(z)$ funksiya hosilasining mavjudligini tasdiqlabgina qolmasdan, uni hisoblash yo'lini ko'rsatadi:

$$f'(z_0) = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + i \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} - i \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - i \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} - i \frac{\partial v}{\partial x}$$

Misol. $f(z) = z^2$ funksiya ixtiyoriy $z \in C$ nuqtada hosilaga ega bo'ladimi?

$$f(z) = (x + iy)^2 = (x^2 - y^2) + i2xy$$

$$u = x^2 - y^2, \quad v = 2xy$$

bu funksiyalar $\forall (x, y) \in R^2$ nuqtada differensiallanuvchi.

Ikkinchi tomondan

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = 2x, \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -2y.$$

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = 2y, \quad \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 2x.$$

bo'lib,

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}, \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial v}{\partial x},$$

Demak, $f(z) = z^2$ funksiya $\forall z \in C$ nuqtada hosilaga ega.

Faraz qilaylik, $f(z) = u(x, y) + iv(x, y)$ funksiya $z_0 = x_0 + iy_0 \in D$, $D(S$ nuqta R^2 da ma'noda differensiallanuvchi bo'lsin. Ushbu $du(x_0, y_0) + idv(x_0, y_0)$

ifoda $f(z)$ funksiyaning z_0 nuqtadagi differensiallanuvchi deyiladi va $df(z_0)$ kabi belgilanadi:

$$df(z_0) = du(x_0, y_0) + idv(x_0, y_0)$$

Ravshanki,

$$du = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} dx - \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} dy,$$

$$dv = \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} dx - \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} dy,$$

Shuni etiborga olib topamiz:

$$df = \left[\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} dx + \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} dy \right] + i \left[\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} dx + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} dy \right] = \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + i \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right) dx + \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + i \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) dy = \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} dx + \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} dy$$

Demak,

$$df = \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} dx + \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} dy$$

Quyidagi $z = x + iy$, $\bar{z} = x - iy$

o'zgaruvchilarni olaylik. Ravshanki,

$$dz = dx + idy,$$

$$d\bar{z} = dx - idy.$$

Bu tengliklardan

$$dx = \frac{1}{2}(dz + d\bar{z}), \quad dy = \frac{1}{2i}(dz - d\bar{z})$$

bo'lishini topamiz.

(7) va (8) tengliklardan

$$df = \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} dx + \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} dy = \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} \frac{1}{2}(dz + d\bar{z}) + \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} \frac{1}{2i}(dz - d\bar{z}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x} - i \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} \right) dz + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x} + i \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} \right) d\bar{z}$$

bo'lishi kelib chiqadi.

Agar

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial z} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x} - i \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x} + i \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - i \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)$$

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial \bar{z}} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x} + i \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x} - i \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + i \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)$$

ko'rinishda belgilansa unda $f(z)$ funksiya differensiyali uchun ushbu

$$df = \frac{\partial f}{\partial z} dz + \frac{\partial f}{\partial \bar{z}} d\bar{z}$$

tenglikka kelamiz.

Aytaylik, $u(x, y)$ va $v(x, y)$ funksiyalar biror nuqtada Koshi-Riman shartlarini bajarsin:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}, \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial v}{\partial x},$$

Unda (9) tenglikka ko'ra, shu nuqtada $\frac{\partial f}{\partial \bar{z}} = 0$. Aksincha, $f(z)$ funksiya uchun

biror nuqtada $\frac{\partial f}{\partial \bar{z}} = 0$

bo'lsin. Ravshanki (9) tenglikka ko'ra shu nuqtada

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}, \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial v}{\partial x},$$

bo'ladi.

Demak, biror nuqta da Koshi-Riman shartlarining bajarilishi shu nuqta $\frac{\partial f}{\partial \bar{z}} = 0$ da tenglikning o'rinli bo'lishiga ekivalent ekan.

Agar $W = f(z)$ funksiya nuqtada hosilaga ega bo'lsa, shu nuqtada $\frac{\partial f}{\partial \bar{z}} = 0$ bo'lib,

funksiyaning hosilasi $f'(z_0) = \frac{\partial f}{\partial z}$ differensiyali esa

$$df = \frac{\partial f}{\partial z} dz = f'(z_0) dz$$

ko'rinishda bo'ladi.

Kompleks analizda hosilaga ega bo'lgan funksiyalar C-differensiyallanuvchi funksiyalar deyiladi.

Faraz qilaylik, $W = f(z)$ funksiya biror $D \subset S$ (S sohada berilgan bo'lsin).

4-ta'rif: Agar $f(z)$ funksiya $z_0 \in D$ nuqtaning biror $U(z_0, \varepsilon) \subset D$ atrofida C-differensiyalanuvchi bo'lsa, $f(z)$ nuqtada gollomorf (yoki analitik) deb ataladi.

5-ta'rif: Agar $f(z)$ funksiya D soxoning har bir nuqtasida golomorf bo'lsa,

funksiya D sohada golomorf deyiladi.

Odatda D sohada golomorf bo'lgan funksiyalar sinfi $\mathfrak{G}(D)$ kabi belgilanadi.

6-ta'rif: Agar $g(z) = f\left(\frac{1}{z}\right)$ funksiya $z=0$ nuqtada golomorf bo'lsa, $f(z)$ funksiya ∞ nuqtada golomorf deyiladi.

7-ta'rif: Agar $\overline{f(z)}$ funksiya z_0 (D nuqtada golomorf bo'lsa, $f(z)$ funksiya z_0 nuqta da antigolomorf deyiladi.

Aytaylik, R^2 fazodagi $E \subset R^2$ sohada $F = F(x, y)$ funksiya berilgan bo'lib, u shu sohada ikkinchi tartibli uzluksiz hususiy hosilalarga

$$\frac{\partial^2 F(x, y)}{\partial x^2}, \quad \frac{\partial^2 F(x, y)}{\partial y^2}$$

ega bo'lsin.

8-ta'rif: Agar E sohaning har bir nuqtasida

$$\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial y^2} = 0$$

tenglik bajarilsa, $F(x, y)$ funksiya E sohada garmonik funksiya deyiladi.

Odatda (10) Laplas tenglamasi deyiladi va quyidagicha yoziladi:

$$\Delta F = 0,$$

bunda $\Delta = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}$

Loplas operatori uchun

$$\Delta = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} - i \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} + i \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right) = 4 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z \partial \bar{z}}$$

bo'lishini etiborga olsak, unda (10) tenglikni quyidagicha yozish mumkin.

$$\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial z \partial \bar{z}} = 0$$

4-teorema. $D(S)$ sohaga golomorf bo'lgan har qanday $f(z)$ funksiyaning haqiqiy

hamda mavhum qismlari shu sohada garmonik bo'ladi.

Isbot. Aytaylik, $f(z) = u(x, y) + iv(x, y)$ funksiya D sohada golomorf bo'lsin. Unda

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}, \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial v}{\partial x}, \text{ tengliklar bajariladi.}$$

Bu tengliklardan foydalanib topamiz:

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} = \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y \partial x}, \quad \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} = -\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x \partial y},$$

Agar

$$\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y \partial x} = \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x \partial y},$$

bo'lishini e'tiborga olsak, u holda yuqoridagi tengliklardan

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} = 0,$$

bo'lishi kelib chiqadi. Bu esa $u(x, y)$ funksiyaning garmonik ekanini bildiradi.

Xuddi shunga o'xshash $v(x, y)$ funksiyaning garmonikligi ko'rsatiladi. Teorema isbot bo'ldi.

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